

**FACTORS AFFECTING THE UPTAKE OF BREAST CANCER
SCREENING PROGRAMMES AMONG RURAL WOMEN IN
GWAGWALADA AREA COUNCIL OF THE FEDERAL CAPITAL
TERRITORY, (F C T) ABUJA- NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT

This study was designed to examine the possible barriers to effective breast cancer screening uptake among rural women. The study explored barriers related to the uptake of breast cancer screening among rural women five communities namely Dupka, Dobi, Ibwa, Paiko and Kaida in Gwagwalada Area council of the FCT. The objective of this study was to evaluate the factors that hinder the uptake of breast cancer screening among women in rural communities. A quantitative research design was used. Quantitative information as well as focused group discussion were engaged to ensure maximal information were extracted from the respondents. A total of 804 participants were engaged in this study. Data obtained from the focus group discussions and in-depth interviews were analyzed. Finding from the study indicated eight categorical barrier that affect the uptake of breast cancer screen among rural women. They include; hospital-related (74.1%), economic (99.0%), geographical (97.5%), educational (78.6%) , sociocultural practices (63.6%), spousal decision (66.0%), gender of the health provider conducting the screening (86.8%), and religious barriers (88.1). The study concluded to ensure effective uptake of breast cancer screening programmes, there is the need to address the identified barriers, the involve spouses, religious and cultural leaders in the planning and implementation of breast cancer screening programmes. The study further suggested that breast cancer screening services should be integrated into the services of primary healthcare centres to make it more effective.

INTRODUCTION

Cancer is a large group of diseases that can start in almost any organ or tissue of the body due to the uncontrollable growth of abnormal cells beyond their usual boundaries to invade adjoining parts of the body and/or spread to other organs (WHO 2023). It is a disease process that begins when an abnormal cells is transformed by the genetic mutation of the cellular Deoxyribonucleic acids (DNA) (Azenha et al , 2011). They can also be referred to as neoplasm and malignant tumour. It is thus a disease in which abnormal cells divide uncontrollably and destroy body tissue. This could result in tumors, damage to the immune system, and other impairment that can be fatal. Cancer can affect various parts of the body, such as the breasts, lungs, prostate, and skin. Though cancer is a broad term, it describes the disease that results when cellular changes cause the uncontrolled growth and division of cells.

Further reports from WHO (2023), revealed that cancer is the second leading cause of death globally, accounting for an estimated 9.6 million deaths, or 1 in 6 deaths, since 2018. Lung, prostate, colorectal, stomach and liver cancer are the most common types of cancer in men, while breast, colorectal, lung, cervical and thyroid cancer are the most common among women. They opined that the cancer burden continues to grow globally, exerting tremendous physical, emotional and financial strain on individuals, families, communities and health systems. They averred that many health systems in low- and middle-income countries are least prepared to manage this burden, and large numbers of cancer patients globally do not have access to timely quality diagnosis and treatment, however, the report revealed that In countries where health systems are strong, survival rates of many types of cancers are improving thanks to accessible early detection, quality treatment and survivorship care.

Breast cancer has been reported as the most common cancer among women, and is believed to comprise about 23% of the female cancers (Haque et al., 2016). They opined that one in eight women born today will be diagnosed with breast cancer at some time in her life as the incidence rate of breast cancer is rapidly increasing in developing countries due to increased life expectancy, growing urbanization, adoption of western lifestyle, especially in younger women. As indicated by (Eltwansy, 2018) about half of all breast cancer (BC) cases occur in developing countries, with a 43% mortality rate compared to 30% in developed countries. Breast cancer has become a serious public health challenge globally with over one million new cases diagnosed annually, resulting in over 400,000 annual death and about 4.4 million women living with the disease (Okobia and Bunker, 2006). According to WHO, (2007), breast cancer is about the most common form of cancer among women in both high and low resource setting countries. In the opinion of Ferlay et 'al (2008), breast cancer has become the most common malignancy and first cause of cancer mortality in women worldwide with new cases estimated at 1,384,155 in 2008 and with a rising worldwide prevalence.

Globally, breast cancer has been implicated as a major leading cause of death among women (Sasco, 2008) as about 875,000 deaths in more than a million cases of breast cancer is reported annually especially in developing countries. WHO, (2022) reported that breast cancer caused 685 000 deaths globally in 2020 and that roughly half of all breast cancers occur in women with no

specific risk factors other than sex and age while approximately 0.5–1% of breast cancers occur in men. It is thus important to note that breast cancer occurs in every country in the world.

The office of national Statistics in the United Kingdom (2014) reported that breast cancer is the most common cancer in the United Kingdom and the second most common cause of cancer death in women, after lung cancer. It indicated that breast cancer is one of the three cancers including cervical and bowel cancers that have national screening programmes in the United Kingdom.

Moreover, a population-based study of cancer survival in Africa, Asia and Central America reported a low breast cancer survival rate in African countries especially in Gambia with a survival rate of about 12% (Sankaranarayanan, et al 2010). Clegg-Lampsey et al, (2009) reported that in Ghana, breast cancer deaths were estimated annually at 16.5% of all women cancer deaths. While Okobia et al (2006) reported that in Nigeria, breast cancer accounted for 56.6% of all cancer diagnosis between 1995 and 2002.

Though breast cancer is neither painful nor cause any discomfort in its early stage, presents as a painless breast lump, there are diverse risk factors that may affect each woman's susceptibility to the disease. The burden of the disease has been on the increase and affected women often present late in hospitals when the disease has reached advance stage as averred by Anderson et al (2010). As such, its treatment and management at this stage becomes seriously compromised; hence, El Saghir et al (2011) attributed the poor survival rate to late detection and diagnosis.

Besides poverty, several barriers have been linked to breast cancer control in LMICs where women seek medical help late and cancers are often diagnosed at advanced stages when very little can be done in terms of curative treatment. Understanding of these barriers and how they can be ameliorated is this focus of this study.

1.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Various intervention programmes to improve breast cancer awareness among women across age range and settings have been undertaken by various agencies of government and non-governmental organizations. However, the impact of these efforts at improving the awareness, screening and control of breast cancer in Nigeria has not yielded much results especially among women in rural communities. This study is thus designed to investigate the barriers to breast cancer awareness and screen among women in rural communities of Dobi, Passo, Dupka and Kaida in Gwagwalada Area Council of the Federal Capital Territory Abuja, Nigeria in order to properly evaluate how these barriers can be eliminated so that breast cancer intervention programmes can yield the desired results among women in these rural settings.

The objective of the study is thus to examine the barriers to breast cancer screening among women in rural settings in order to enhance the prevention of breast cancer amongst Nigerian women.

Some of the specific objectives include;

1. What is the level of awareness of breast cancer among rural women
2. How knowledgeable are rural women about breast cancer?
3. What is the opinion of rural women on breast cancer screening?
4. What factors constitute barriers to the effective uptake of breast cancer screening programmes among rural women?
5. How could these factors be eliminated to enhance the uptake of breast cancer screening programmes among rural women.

Findings from this study will potentially contribute to the enhancement best practices in the implementation of breast cancer awareness and screening in future public health interventions. It will also help provide information to enhance breast cancer screening uptake. This study will identify and appraise some of the factors militating against public health breast cancer awareness and screening campaigns and make evidence- based recommendations on how breast cancer awareness and screening campaigns and interventions can be improved to become more result oriented. The study will objectively highlight areas where further research may be required to improve breast cancer awareness, screening uptake and general enhanced health outcomes.

The focus of this study is principally on the barriers to effective breast cancers screening uptake among rural women and how it affects the overall breast cancer prevention programme in Nigeria. This study was therefore limited to rural women across 5 rural communities in Gwagwalada Area Council of the F C T. Abuja Nigeria

2.0 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Research Design

The design adopted for this study is an exploratory quantitative design. This involved the use of in-depth interviews and focus group discussion (FGD) sessions with the participants.

2.2 Research Setting

This study was conducted among rural dwelling women in Dukpa, Paiko, Ibwa, Dobi and Kaida communities within Gwagwalada Area Council of the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. These were dwelling places identified as existing communities in the official gazette of the FCT. Traditional, religious and opinion leaders within the communities were consulted for their consent and cooperation during the period of the study.

2.3 Research Instrument

A structured questionnaire and focused group discussion were used as research instrument for this study. The instrument was structured to provoke specific information from the respondents during the in-depth interviews and focus group discussion (FGD) sessions with the participants. The structured questionnaire consisted of variables on social demographics of the respondents, their knowledge on breast cancer, attitude and practice of breast cancer screening and perceived factors affecting their uptake of breast cancer screening programmes. Five FGD sessions were held with groups comprising of the various age brackets predetermined for the study in each of the communities.

All interview and FGD sessions had an interpreter for easy interaction and responses were transcribed verbatim with participants' permission. Confidentiality of information provided and anonymity of participants were maintained with proper assurances on these were given to the participants during the process. Preliminary visits were conducted to ensure earlier familiarity with the participants and build credibility before the in-depth and FGD sessions while prolonged investigation strategies were used to establish trust.

2.4 Study Population and Sampling

The study population for this study consisted of 804 women selected among women resident within the five (5) communities selected for this study. The respondents were divided into various focus discussing groups for effectiveness and efficiency. Purposive sampling was used to identify subjects for in-depth investigation to ensure a clear understanding of the issue of enquiry.

2.5 Data Collection

Data were collected during each interview and FGD session. These data thereafter vetted, sorted and subjected to statistical analysis

2.6 Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using simple descriptive statistics. Categorical variables were presented in frequency (n) and proportions in percentages (%) for clarity and easy understanding.

2.7 Ethical Consideration

Ethical approval was obtained from the FCT Health Research Ethics Committee before the study commenced. Each participant was clearly informed on the content and context of the study for consent and participation was voluntary.

3.0 RESULT AND ANALYSIS OF FINDINGS

The findings from this study are presented in frequencies and percentages for clarity and easy understanding.

3.1.1 SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF PARTICIPANTS.

The socio-demographic characteristics of respondents are as indicated in table 1 below

TABLE 1: SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF PARTICIPANTS.

VARIABLE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
AGE		
21-30	266	33.1
31-40	254	31.6
41-50	162	20.1
51-60	101	12.6
61 and above	21	2.6
MARITAL STATUS		
SINGLE	81	10.1
MARRIED	568	70.6
DIVORCED	86	10.7
WIDOWED	69	8.6
LEVEL OF EDUCATION		
NO FORMAL EDUCATION	55	6.8
PRIMARY SCHOOL	482	60.0
SECONDARY SCHOOL	231	28.7
POSTSECONDARY	36	4.5
INCOME LEVEL		

HIGH	48	6.0
MODERATE	196	24.3
LOW	560	69.7
OCCUPATION		
UNEMPLOYED	61	7.6
EMPLOYED (PRIVATE SECTOR)	73	9.1
EMPLOYED (PUBLIC SECTOR)	262	32.6
FARMING	408	50.7
RELIGION		
CHRISTIANITY	308	38.3
ISLAM	485	60.3
OTHERS	11	1.4

Findings from table 1 indicated that participants within the age bracket of 21-30 constituted 33.1% of the study population, those of 31-40 bracket made up 31.6%, those 41-50 (20.1%), those 51-60 (12.6%) while those 61 and above constituted 2.6%.

Participants who were single comprised 10.1% of the population, those married were 70.6%, the separated among them made up 10.7% of the population while those widowed among the participant were 8.6%. Also, while 60.0% of them had primary education as their highest level at the moment, 28.7% (secondary), 4.5% (Postsecondary) and 6.8% had no formal education. Similarly, 38.3% of them were Christians, 60.3% were Muslims and 1.4% practiced other religion.

Furthermore, 7.6% of the study population were unemployed, 9.1% were employed in the private sector, 32.6% were engaged in the public sector, while 50.7% were predominantly farmers. Also, 69.7% of the participant were categorized into the low-income bracket, 24.3 in the moderate and 6.0% in the high-income bracket.

3.1.2 KNOWLEDGE OF BREAST CANCER

The knowledge score of the participants is as indicated in table 2.

TABLE 2: KNOWLEDGE OF RESPONDENTS OF BREAST CANCER

KNOWLEDGE VARIABL	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
a. Awareness of Breast Cancer	252	31.3
b. Symptoms	131	52.0
c. Risk factor	79	31.3

d. Prevention	63	25.0
e. Management	42	16.7

As shown in table 2; among the study population, only 31.3% were aware of breast cancer. Among those that were aware of breast cancer, 52.0% were aware of the sign and symptoms of breast cancer, 31.3% were aware of the risk factors in breast cancer, 25.0% of the prevention while 16.7% were aware of the management of breast cancer.

3.1.3 FACTORS AFFECTING THE EFFECTIVE UPTAKE BREAST CANCER SCREENING PROGRAMMES

Factors affecting the effective uptake of breast cancer screening are as outlined in table 3.

TABLE 3: FACTORS AFFECTING THE EFFECTIVE UPTAKE BREAST CANCER SCREENING PROGRAMMES

S/N	VARIABLE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1	Economic/Financial Geographic	796	99.0
2	Location of test center	784	97.5
3	Gender of the Health Care Provider	698	86.8
4	Educational	632	78.6
5	Religion	708	88.1
6	Spouse Decision	531	66.0
7	Sociocultural Practices	511	63.6
8	Hospital Related	596	74.1

From table 3, respondents indicated that some of factors that constitute barriers to the effective uptake of breast cancer screening programmes include; Economic/Financial Barriers (99.0%), Location of Screening Centres (97.5%), Gender of the health worker conducting the screening exercise (86.8%), Education (78.6%), Religion (75.6%), Spouse decision (63.6%), Sociocultural practices (63.6%), Hospital related challenges (74.1%).

4.0 DISCUSSION

This study was designed to explore the opinion of women in rural communities on barriers to breast cancer screening uptake. The findings from this study revealed the following as the basic factors militating against the effective uptake of breast cancer screening among women resident in rural communities.

- **ECONOMIC/ FINANCIAL FACTORS:** This is about the strongest barrier to effective uptake of breast cancer screening programmes as findings showed that 99% of the women indicated this as a militating factor. Some of the financial constraints mention by the participants indicated the cost of transportation to the screening centres which has been compounded by the current excruciating cost of transportation, high cost of living and insufficient financial resources as many rural women are within the low income bracket. This is similar to earlier finding reported by Chidyaonga-Maseko et al, (2015).
- **LOCATION OF SCREENING CENTRES:** Most screening centres are located in the urban or semi-urban areas which automatically keeps it out of the reach of rural women. Thus, bearing in mind the high cost of transportation and other travel costs systematically presents a serious barrier to the uptake of breast cancer screening programmes by women resident in rural communities.
- **GENDER OF THE HEALTHCARE PROVIDER:** Over 80% of women in this study indicated that most times when they visit healthcare facilities, most workers there are predominantly males. As such, they feel discouraged to go for breast cancer screening as they expressed some reservation towards voluntary exposure of their breast to male healthcare workers.
- **RELIGION:** Just like the gender related factor, religious beliefs and practices constitute a major barrier to the effective uptake of breast cancer screening programmes among most Christians and Muslims. Some Muslim women would not allow male screeners to attend to them in the hospital except in inevitable circumstance. This thus constitute a serious militating factor against the effective uptake of breast cancer screening.
- **EDUCATION:** The level of education both of the women and their spouses was identified as a factor that can negatively impact on the uptake of breast cancer screening. This can be linked to limited or lack of appropriate health information on breast cancer among the women and men at the rural communities. They are simply of the opinion that there is no need for healthy looking women to visit hospitals for a check-up of any form as such visits are basically for sick people or at most pregnant women. This poor information on breast cancer screening thus militates against the effective uptake of breast cancer screening programmes.
- **SPOUSE DECISION:** Most women in this study indicated that the approval of their husband is essential before they can embark on something as serious as breast cancer screening. This dependence of Spousal decision for most rural women to undertake breast cancer screening could constitute a militating factor against uptake especially when such spouses are not well informed to make such decision. Also, most of the women reported that their spouses will need to provide the funds needed for them to undertake the screening besides the approval.
- **SOCIOCULTURAL PRACTICES:** some cultural beliefs and practices also constitute barriers to effective uptake of breast cancer screening programmes. Some rural dwellers prefer herbal treatment to orthodox medicine and as such will not willingly participate in breast cancer screening programmes. Also, some cultural beliefs have strange connotations to issues like breast cancer such even the rural will not readily participate in breast cancer screening as they can be described as wayward. Such a situation leads to fear of the test result by rural women and promotes refusal to participate in breast cancer screening programmes.

- **HOSPITAL RELATED FACTORS:** Some hospital related factors the militate against the effective uptake of breast cancer screening programmes include long hospital waiting time which affects their work, business or farming time, cost implication of the screening and the attitude of some healthcare workers. Others include poor healthcare infrastructure, and lack of trained personnel.

5.0 CONCLUSION

Findings from this study showed that some of the factors that hinders the effective uptake of breast cancer screening among women in rural communities; economic/financial factors, location of screening centres, gender of the healthcare worker conducting the screening, education/ level of information about breast cancer, waiting for spouse's approval, religion, sociocultural factors and some hospital- related factors.

It is thus essential to address these factors frontally in order to improve the uptake of breast cancer screening among women in rural communities. This will enhance early detection, reduce risks and prevent avoidable breast cancer related deaths.

From the foregoing the following suggestions are recommended to enhance the uptake of breast cancer screening among women in rural communities:

1. The government should ensure that breast cancer screening is free and all efforts should be made to sustain it.
2. Specific days should be dedicated for breast cancer screening across Primary healthcare facilities to improve access
3. The Area Councils should provide transportation for women willing to participate in the screening exercise
4. More female healthcare workers should be training and deployed for effective breast cancer screening.
5. Efforts should be made to provide breast cancer health education to both men and women in rural communities to improve understanding about the disease and make spouses' approval easier.
6. Community and religious leaders in communities should be carried along in breast cancer awareness campaigns for proper enlightenment, sustainability of breast cancer programmes and most importantly, to reduce sociocultural interferences to breast cancer screening.
7. Efforts should be sustained at the infrastructural improvement of facilities across PHC centres.
8. Regular training programmes should be organized to improve the knowledge and skill of healthcare workers recent trend in breast cancer prevention and management.

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